

1 HSV-1 ICP22 activates C21orf91.

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6 The HSV-1 genome contains dozens of viral gene products. We measured total transcription by
7 RNA-sequencing in human cells expressing doxycycline-inducible ICP22 to discover novel functions and
8 network interaction partners of ICP22. We describe here control of *C21orf91* by ICP22. We used
9 proteomics to describe functionally important cellular activity involving ICP22 and C21orf91 by discovery of
10 C21orf91 protein interaction partners. C21orf91 protein could bind CDC23, CCDC85B mitochondrial
11 effector OIP5 and the F-box protein Fbx17, which controlled a Skp-Cul-Fbox complex.

12 Citations

13 1. Wong, J.C., Bryant, V., Lamprecht, T., Ma, J., Walsh, M., Schwartz, J., del pilar Alzamora, M.,
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15 mutations are associated with extensive genetic evolution and diverse hematologic outcomes. *JCI insight*,
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